

Primary and secondary stress responses to grading and hauling in rainbow trout, *Salmo gairdneri*

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Abstract

Differential increases in plasma cortisol 1 h after disturbance reflected both the difference in severity between grading and hauling and the additive effect of the two treatments together on this primary response. The transient nature of the physiological responses and the lack of haematological changes indicated that neither grading nor hauling represented severe stress to the fish.